

MIDDLE-LATE HOLOCENE COOLING INCREASED THE SOIL CARBON STOCKS IN AN ARCTIC-ALPINE ENVIRONMENT ON VARANGER PENINSULA (NORWAY)

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INTRODUCTION

The climate is changing rapidly with increases in near surface air temperatures almost everywhere globally, and especially in the Arctic (Pörtner *et al.*, 2022). A big contribution to the climatic changes of the current era comes from the anthropogenic emissions of atmospheric carbon in the form of CO₂, however, carbon is also stored in the Earth's crust, the oceans, and the terrestrial ecosystem. A particularly relevant carbon pool concerns the northern circumpolar permafrost region, and a series of recent reviews have been conducted with the purpose of estimating the current carbon stocks of its soils (Tarnocai *et al.*, 2009; Hugelius *et al.*, 2014). However, the focus there was purely on permafrost environments, leaving a gap on the soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks and distribution in non-permafrost cold periglacial landscapes. Kvitnesfjell, located in NW Varanger Peninsula (N Norway), is a hilly cold periglacial environment that lacks permafrost, but includes landforms such as wetlands, earth and peat hummocks, and solifluction. To our understanding, this is the first detailed SOC inventory of a cold periglacial area that lacks permafrost. The main objectives are to (1) conduct a detailed field SOC inventory and calculate the mean SOC stocks at landscape level, (2) identify the areas and landforms that store high amounts of SOC (carbon hotspots), (3) determine when these landforms were formed, and (4) discuss the potential vulnerability of these carbon hotspots to climate change.

METHODS

Five transects were selected and the sampling sites were placed along these transects at strictly equidistant intervals. Soil samples were collected, and a description of land cover was made in situ before sampling. Additionally, solifluction features were analysed in greater detail. The soil samples were then analysed for the parameters crucial for the estimation of SOC stocks. Some subsamples were also sent for elemental analyses to get C and N contents, while some were sent for ¹⁴C dating for the paleoenvironmental reconstruction of the study area. A high-resolution satellite image was then used for a land cover classification of the 9 classes mentioned in Table 1, and the weighed mean SOC stock values of each class were upscaled to the whole study area of 21.7 km².

RESULTS

Wetlands hold the highest SOC values at full depth with 37.1 ± 21.3 kg C m⁻², however, they cover only 8.3% of the total study area (Table 1). Dry heath tundra dominates the landscape (33.7%), and the mean SOC is 5.46 ± 4.19 kg C m⁻². The SOC stocks in Kvitnesfjell lie in between the values from other permafrost and periglacial mountainous and hilly areas. They are not so high to consider the area a carbon hotspot, however, in some cases, values even above 50 kg C m⁻² are observed, with a maximum value found at a wetland site (97.5 kg C m⁻²). Unique periglacial features like solifluction lobes and earth hummocks also hold significant amounts of carbon. Wetlands have basal dates ranging between 7088-119 cal yr BP, earth hummocks between 4363-1644 cal yr BP, and buried organic layers in solifluction lobes range in age between 5250-350 cal yr BP. These ¹⁴C dates show that these landforms are all of Middle to Late Holocene age, a period associated with colder and wetter conditions based on proxy analyses of lake sediments in the

region (Huntley et al., 2013). This cooling and increased moisture of the climate increased the carbon sink capacity in Kvitnesfjell.

Table 1. Plant and soil attributes and SOC storage (kg C m⁻²) for the 0-30 cm and 0-100 cm depth intervals for each land cover class (means and standard deviations), and for total study area (weighed means and confidence intervals).

Land Cover	% cover in study area	Sites (n)	% plant cover (mean ± sd)	% stones ^a (mean ± sd)	Soil depth in cm (mean ± sd)	SOC 0-30 in kg C m ⁻² (mean ± sd)	SOC 0-100 in kg C m ⁻² (mean ± sd)
Open Water	0.29	4	5 ± 12	72 ± 19	2.6 ± 2.7	0.17 ± 0.27	0.17 ± 0.27
Bare Grounds	7.09	4	10 ± 9	45 ± 34	23 ± 9	0.94 ± 0.79	0.94 ± 0.79
Sparse Tundra	25.1	5	66 ± 20	29 ± 12	19 ± 9	2.99 ± 0.71	3.01 ± 0.76
Dry Heath Tundra	33.7	13	114 ± 9	1 ± 2	38 ± 26	4.38 ± 2.23	5.46 ± 4.19
Mesic Tundra	5.62	2	130 ± 14	0 ± 0	55 ± 47	8.38 ± 3.25	11.5 ± 7.64
Earth Hummocks	13.4	6	119 ± 7	0 ± 0	34 ± 15	16.8 ± 9.90	18.0 ± 10.6
Grass Tundra	6.38	2	120 ± 0	0 ± 0	31 ± 4	7.11 ± 1.38	7.50 ± 1.94
Tall Shrub	0.15	1	130	0	82	6.57	16.8
Wetlands	8.30	4	109 ± 22	0 ± 0	61 ± 14	13.7 ± 5.94	37.1 ± 21.3
Study area	100	41				6.61 ± 1.28^b	9.31 ± 2.30^b

^a Stones >4 cm diameter at surface, ^b Weighed averages with confidence intervals

CONCLUSIONS

This study is a detailed SOC inventory at landscape level in a cold periglacial tundra area without permafrost, something that has not been done before. The periglacial landforms found in Kvitnesfjell are of Middle to Late Holocene age, related to the cooling that took place after the Holocene Thermal Maximum. The results indicate that the cooling increased the carbon sink properties of the area. Considering the future climatic changes in the Arctic, with increased temperatures and precipitation, the carbon sink in the study area is expected to decrease.

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